

Self-Supervised Pre-Training for Digital Dermatology & Data-Centric Approach to Medical Imaging

A thesis to attain the degree of
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Content Warning. This work uses data from various dermatology diseases that might be disturbing to see. Please be forewarned.

Declaration of originality. I hereby declare that I have prepared the present work independently and have used nothing other than the specified aids. All text sections, citations or contents of other authors used have been explicitly marked as such.

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Abstract

Training supervised models requires large amounts of labelled data, whose creation is often expensive and time-consuming, especially in the medical domain. The standard practice to mitigate the lack of annotated medical images is to use transfer learning and fine-tune supervised pre-trained ImageNet weights on a downstream task. While this approach achieves satisfactory performance, it still requires a large dataset to adjust the global features for a specific task. Another way to tackle data scarcity in the medical field is by simplifying the data collection process and ordering health workers to document skin conditions. However, this approach usually leads to image collections containing contaminations such as irrelevant samples, duplicates and label errors since this is in stark contrast to prior practice where experts collected samples in standardised conditions.

This thesis aims to contribute to the research landscape of deep learning in combination with digital dermatology by producing three scientific articles in the domains of self-supervised learning and dataset cleaning. The first subproject, termed *Self-supervised pre-training for dermatological imaging*, investigated the possible benefits of using domain-specific self-supervised pre-training for digital dermatology by comparing them against supervised and self-supervised general-purpose pre-training. The second subproject, termed *Data-centric approach to medical imaging*, introduced a novel semi-automatic data cleaning strategy which can detect various dataset contaminations.

The results of the first subproject indicated a clear benefit in using domain-specific self-supervised pre-trained features in terms of reducing the need for annotated samples and increasing linear, kNN and fine-tuning performance for classification and segmentation tasks. Further, a qualitative evaluation revealed that domain-specific pre-training learned more favourable properties for applications in dermatology since it included both local and global features. The results of the second subproject showed that the novel dataset cleaning method is competitive with baseline methods across multiple contamination ratios and datasets. However, the method's performance of label error detection is significantly lower than for the other contamination categories, indicating that there is room for improving the technique. The proposed method was then applied to well-known dermatology benchmarks and found multiple issues in training and test sets, thus destabilising them.

The thesis resulted in three scientific articles almost ready for submission describing the results and insights from the two subprojects. The articles from the first subproject should help advance the paradigm shift from using general-purpose features to using domain-specific self-supervised pre-trained ones. The submission from the second subproject introduced a novel data-cleaning method targeted towards medical imaging to help practitioners in this field produce high-quality image collections.

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Chapter 1

Introduction

Current artificial intelligence applications for medical imaging often rely on convolutional neural networks (CNNs) trained in a supervised way. These models have shown remarkable performance across many medical tasks due to their ability to deal with raw image data (Brinker et al., 2019). However, CNNs typically demand vast amounts of annotated data to achieve the high performance and robustness required in this field. In the medical domain, annotated samples can be hard to obtain, caused mainly by the high cost of acquiring expert annotations (Castro et al., 2020), the difficulty of getting multiple experts to agree on an answer (Jacob et al., 2021), the issue of finding rare conditions, collection processes that need to tackle selection biases (Groh et al., 2021) and typically require specialised equipment, and annotation processes which often need to follow strict regulations. Although diagnoses are reported in patient files, one typically needs to recruit and train several dermatologists to do a tedious labelling job since the information in these files is too coarse, and more details are required. This leads to the fact that the most popular general-purpose image dataset, ImageNet (Deng et al., 2009), has 200 times more pictures than the biggest public dermoscopy dataset (ISIC, 2016) and 2000 times more than the largest public clinical image collection (Groh et al., 2021).

Data scarcity in the medical domain is often tackled by using transfer learning, which can leverage knowledge from a source task with plenty of data to perform a target task where data is limited. The most common approach to transfer learning in computer vision is pre-training large models such as residual neural networks (ResNets) or vision transformers (ViTs) on massive labelled image collections such as the 14-million-strong ImageNet database (Deng et al., 2009). Pre-training on ImageNet is widely used in the medical domain to compensate for the lack of image data and improve robustness (Jeong et al., 2023). However, this is a suboptimal approach since features extracted from natural images may not be ideal representations for some medical contexts since pre-trained ImageNet models tend to focus on global objects. However, in many medical contexts, local features such as textures are equally important (Matsoukas et al., 2022). In recent years, there has been a paradigm shift from supervised to self-supervised pre-training. Self-supervised learning (SSL) is a way of learning from data without explicit instructions or labels. Instead, it learns patterns from the data and uses them to perform a task, thus not inheriting any biases present in the labels (Shurrab and Duwairi, 2021). Recently SSL became popular in the medical domain as large volumes of unlabelled data are more accessible than their annotated counterparts. Several works have demonstrated the effectiveness of this approach for classification (Li et al., 2021), localisation (Sowrirajan et al., 2021), and segmentation (Xie et al., 2020). However, while transfer learning from supervised (Raghu et al., 2019) and self-supervised pre-trained (Truong et al., 2021) ImageNet features are widely studied, the transferability and influence of self-supervised pre-training directly on dermatology images is not.

Another way to tackle data scarcity in the medical domain is by simplifying the underlying collection process and ordering health workers to document skin conditions with digital photography. However, while this approach is widely used in practice, it usually leads to image collections of mediocre quality since it involves significant amounts of manual work, which is prone to errors (Sambasivan et al., 2021). Often, these collections contain problems such as irrelevant samples, duplicates and labelling mistakes. Although these issues might not significantly impact models when trained in combination with larger datasets, these mistakes can lead to various problems in low-data regimes. For example, models being incorrectly evaluated and decisions being taken on potentially flawed arguments. Thus, there has been a growing need for general procedures to assess the quality of datasets and clean predominant mistakes semi-automatically.

1.1 Research Questions and Expected Results

This thesis consists of two main subprojects, namely *self-supervised pre-training for digital dermatology* and *a data-centric approach to medical imaging*. For the first subproject, the University Hospital of Basel has provided an unlabelled dataset of approximately 250'000 dermatology images. These images originate from public and private dataset collections from various hospitals worldwide. This project examines if using self-supervised learning can yield better parameter initialisations for transfer learning than supervised and self-supervised pre-training on ImageNet. Additionally, this project wants to investigate if using SSL can help mitigate the need for annotated samples in dermatology. By developing a domain-specific pre-training for dermatology, we support current research by the University Hospital of Basel that aims to reduce the need for annotated samples to detect dermatological diseases in third-world countries such as Africa.

For the second subproject, a semi-automatic cleaning pipeline should be developed to find predominant issues in medical datasets, such as irrelevant samples, duplicates and labelling errors. This is mainly motivated by the fact that many data quality issues were found in well-known medical benchmark datasets, thus destabilising them. However, data collection issues are widely found in practice and therefore are one of the primary problems when evaluating machine learning models correctly. By developing such a cleaning pipeline for medical imaging, we support current research by the University Hospital of Basel to enable the assessment and cleaning of collected datasets from health workers in third-world countries to advance approaches to detect diseases in these countries.

The envisaged contributions of this thesis are three scientific articles (almost) ready for submission and written in the corresponding conference and journal templates resulting from the above-described subprojects:

- **Subproject 1:** *Self-supervised pre-training for dermatological imaging* to be submitted to a computer science conference such as MICCAI 2023
- **Subproject 1:** *Self-supervised pre-training for dermatological imaging* to be submitted to a medical journal in dermatology, such as the Journal of Investigative Dermatology (JID)
- **Subproject 2:** *Data-centric approach to medical imaging* to be submitted to a computer science conference such as NeurIPS 2023 Machine Learning for Health (ML4H)

1.2 Report Structure

This thesis is structured in the format of a paper dissertation. Hence the documentation will contain the three scientific articles, in a separate chapter, in the template of the respective venue to which they will be submitted. In each of these chapters, there is preliminary background information about the targeted venue, the primary motivation for the article, and the scientific report itself. Additionally, each chapter contains a critical peer review from the author itself and additional ideas or remarks to improve the publication. Finally, in addition to the chapter containing the scientific articles, the thesis includes a general introduction, which presents the current problems of approaches in dermatology, the motivation, research questions, and expected results, and finally, a conclusion, which discusses the outcome of the different articles and describes further research directions of each subproject.

Chapter 2

Investigating Domain-Specific Self-Supervised Learning in Digital Dermatology

This chapter includes a scientific article about domain-specific self-supervised pre-training for dermatological imaging to be submitted to a computer science conference such as MICCAI 2023¹. According to the conference's guidelines, the submitted manuscript should be up to eight pages (text, figures and tables) plus up to two pages of references and no modifications to the template are permitted. The scientific article resulted from the continuation of prior work of the author's specialization project (Gröger, 2022), which was accepted and presented at the IJCAI workshop on Scarce Data in Artificial Intelligence for Healthcare 2022 in Vienna (Gröger et al., 2022).

The primary motivation behind this scientific project was that supervised training requires large amounts of labelled data, whose creation is often expensive and time-consuming, especially in the medical domain. Thus, the standard practice to mitigate the scarcity of annotated medical images is to use transfer learning and fine-tune a general-purpose model, often pre-trained on ImageNet, on the considered task. However, while this approach achieves satisfactory performance, it still requires a substantial amount of labelled data to adapt the pre-trained features for the medical task. A more recent alternative is to apply self-supervised learning on a domain-specific unlabelled dataset and use the resulting features for transfer learning. Thus, this project aimed to investigate if domain-specific self-supervised learning is beneficial for digital dermatology in improving performance and reducing the need for annotated samples.

Remark. The author himself wrote the scientific article. However, multiple co-authors of the paper have contributed to the current report by reviewing, correcting and giving feedback on the points to improve. Additionally, some aspects have been peer-reviewed since the article continues a workshop contribution.

¹<https://conferences.miccai.org/2023/>, accessed on 26.01.2023

Investigating Domain-Specific Self-Supervised Learning in Digital Dermatology

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Abstract. Standard practice to mitigate the scarcity of labelled samples in the medical domain is to adapt generic image classification models, often pre-trained on ImageNet, to the considered clinical task. A more recent alternative is to apply self-supervised learning on a large collection of unlabelled images and to use the resulting model as a starting point. While transfer learning from supervised and self-supervised pre-trained ImageNet features are extensively investigated, there is little study on the effectiveness of domain-specific self-supervised learning in digital dermatology. This paper compares the transferability of five recent self-supervised techniques, ColorMe, SimCLR, BYOL, DINO, and iBOT, pre-trained on a large dermatology dataset against supervised and self-supervised general-purpose features across six selected medical tasks across two families of problems, i.e. classification and segmentation. Our results show that domain-specific self-supervised pre-trained features are beneficial for medical imaging tasks in terms of improving performance and reducing the need for annotated samples. In the most extreme cases, this pre-training regime improved the linear performance by 7%, kNN performance by 8% and fine-tuned performance by 4% compared to the best general-purpose pre-training and, on average, reduced the need for annotated samples by 50%.

Keywords: Self-supervised learning · Transfer learning · Dermatology

1 Introduction

The lack of high-quality annotated data is one of the biggest problems in the medical domain, caused mainly by the high cost of acquiring expert annotations [6], the difficulty of getting multiple experts to agree on an answer [17], the issue of finding rare conditions, collection processes that need to tackle selection biases [14] and annotation processes which often need to follow strict regulations. This leads to the fact that the most popular general-purpose image dataset, ImageNet [10], has 200 times more pictures than the biggest public dermoscopy dataset [16] and 2000 times more than the largest public clinical image

collection [14]. Transfer learning from large supervised pre-trained models on natural images such as ImageNet has become standard practice to tackle data scarcity in the medical domain [4]. Recently, this approach has been criticised since features extracted from natural images may not be ideal representations for medical applications since they often only consider global features. In contrast, local features, such as textures, are equally or even more meaningful in this context [22]. Recently there has been a growing interest in self-supervised learning (SSL), a hybrid approach relying only on unlabelled data that combines supervised and unsupervised learning. SSL became popular in the medical domain as large volumes of unlabelled data are more accessible than their annotated counterparts. Several works have demonstrated the effectiveness of this approach for classification [19], localisation [30], and segmentation [34]. However, while transfer learning from supervised [26] and self-supervised pre-trained [32] ImageNet features are widely studied, the transferability and influence of self-supervised pre-training directly on dermatology images is not.

The main contributions of this work are the assessment of five self-supervised techniques (ColorMe, SimCLR, BYOL, DINO and iBOT) against three competitive supervised and self-supervised general-purpose baselines. A systematic evaluation of the different methods on four classification- and two segmentation tasks in terms of frozen linear, kNN and fine-tuned performance. Further, the investigation of the influence of domain-specific pre-training in low-data regimes.

2 Related Work

In recent years, self-supervised learning (SSL) has been widely used in computer vision to learn representations without relying on manual annotations. SSL is a hybrid approach that combines supervised and unsupervised learning in a *pre-training-fine-tuning* fashion. It aims at learning semantically useful features by creating a supervised objective from a pool of unlabelled data. The artificial objective is often called the *pretext task*. Learnt features can be used in *downstream tasks* where annotated data is scarce. For a comprehensive review of different SSL methods, we refer to [21], and [29] focusing on medical applications. In this section, we limit ourselves to the methods directly relevant and related to this work.

Many self-supervised learning methods focus on discriminative approaches where each image is considered a separate class, and models are trained to discriminate them. Popular approaches include SimCLR [8], which utilises a contrastive loss to compare different views of the same image, such as transformed versions of the original image, against other randomly sampled images, often called *positive* and *negative samples*, to learn representations robust to variations in the input data. A caveat of these approaches is that they require simultaneously comparing features from numerous images, therefore requiring large batch sizes. Thus, there is interest in approaches that do not depend on discrimination. BYOL [13] is a popular approach that does not require negative sampling and relies on a carefully implemented asymmetric student-teacher ar-

chitecture, where the model learns to match the teacher network’s output with the student’s output. Similarly, DINO [5] compares the probabilities of the outputs from different patches of the same image of a teacher and student network, except that the encoder network is a vision transformer (ViT) [11]. iBOT [35] further builds on these ideas and explicitly exploits inherent properties of ViTs to capture local and global information. Techniques that avoid these general-purpose objectives embed domain-specific bias into their pretext task. One such domain-specific SSL method for medical imaging is ColorMe [20], which uses the task of colourising grayscale images and predicting colour distributions as pretext tasks.

Similar to our work [7] evaluates the influence of different training pipelines in both out-of-distribution and low-data regimes. However, they focus on the effect of both supervised and unsupervised contrastive loss for adapting supervised and self-supervised learned ImageNet features rather than domain-specific self-supervised learning. Similar [32] assess the performance of different SSL methods applied to ImageNet evaluated on multiple medical classification tasks, thus focusing on general-purpose features rather than domain-specific ones. Most close to our paper [3] assessed multiple discriminative SSL methods pre-trained on both medical image datasets and ImageNet and evaluated on two medical classification tasks. Our paper investigates five distinct SSL methods applied to a large-scale pre-training dataset containing dermatological images evaluated on six selected unseen medical tasks, featuring both classification and segmentation.

3 Methodology

Pre-training Data. All self-supervised learning methods were pre-trained on the same data, which includes dermoscopy and clinical images, with the hypothesis that there are common patterns in skin pictures taken at different magnifications. We use 242’039 images from both public and private datasets.

- **Derm7pt** [18] features 2’020 dermoscopy and clinical images of various skin pigmentation lesions.
- **ISIC** [16] is the largest public dermatology dataset. It comprises 107’208 dermoscopy images of pigmented skin lesions and features almost only low-pigmented skin. We explicitly exclude pictures overlapping with HAM10000 [33] and ISIC 2018 task 1 [9] as these are downstream tasks.
- **MED-NODE** [12] features 170 clinical images of pigmented skin lesions collected by the Department of Dermatology of the University Medical Center Groningen in the Netherlands.
- **SD-260** [31] features 12’583 clinical images collected from DermQuest.
- **PH² Database** [23] includes 200 dermoscopy images of pigmented skin lesions obtained at the Dermatology Service of Hospital Pedro Hispano in Matosinhos, Portugal.
- A private dataset of 119’858 clinical images reflecting the data distribution encountered in Swiss hospitals. Pictures were taken using diverse reflex cameras by trained photographers, anonymized and used with approval (EKNZ-2018-01074) from an ethical committee according to Swiss regulations.

Downstream Tasks. We used six downstream tasks not included during pre-training to compare the performance of domain-specific to general-purpose pre-training. Four of the six downstream tasks are open-source, and two are private tasks from the University Hospital of Basel. We ensured that the selected downstream tasks feature some of the challenges present in dermatology, such as different image modalities, e.g. clinical and dermoscopy images, and multi-skin images.

- **PAD-UFES-20** [24] is a public classification dataset composed of clinical images captured by smartphones and a set of clinical patient information. The dataset consists of 1’373 patients, 1’641 skin lesions, and 2’298 images for six different diagnostics.
- **HAM10000** [33] is a public classification dataset consisting of 10’015 dermoscopic images collected from different populations and institutions for seven diagnostic categories of pigmented lesions.
- **Fitzpatrick17k** [14] is a public classification dataset containing 16’577 clinical images, where the highest granularity level of skin condition labels is used as evaluation.
- **BodyLoc** [2] is a private classification task to localise macro-anatomical regions of the body on skin patches. The dataset contains 6’000 anonymised high-resolution clinical images already divided into 29’801 non-overlapping patches showing the main body regions, which only include a single anatomical region and are categorized into six body regions, including an “other” category.
- **ISIC 2018 task 1** [9] is a public segmentation dataset consisting of 2’594 dermoscopic images of skin lesions segmentation boundaries, i.e. binary segmentation. Each image contains one primary lesion. The test set used in this work differs from the original challenge because only three submissions are allowed per user, thus would limit the number of experiments.
- **PPP** [1] is a private segmentation task to detect palmoplantar pustular psoriasis (PPP). The dataset contains 151 anonymised high-resolution clinical images divided into 3’624 non-overlapping patches captured at the University Hospital Zurich and a pixel-wise annotation of four categories.

If no validation set was available for a downstream task, the training data was randomly split into a training and validation set with sizes of 85% and 15%. The final evaluation was performed on the test set defined by the authors, if available. However, if no designated test set was introduced, an additional split of 15% is used. Whenever available, the split was done on a patient level to ensure no train-test leak.

Implementation. The self-supervised learning (SSL) methods used in this work can be split into two groups based on the encoder architecture, which can either be a CNN or a ViT. We used the same encoder to ensure a fair comparison within these groups. To further promote the correspondence between the two groups, we selected architectures that perform similarly on ImageNet.

For the CNN-based encoders, we chose ResNet-50 (RN-50) [15], and for the ViT-based, a ViT-Tiny (ViT-T) [11] with patch size of 16×16 . The RN-50 has roughly 23 Mio. trainable parameters, and the ViT-T 5.4 Mio. Each method’s configurations, such as method-specific parameters and augmentation technique, followed the introductory paper. The model input is resized to 224×224 pixels and normalized using the mean and standard deviation of ImageNet [10]. All models are trained until the validation loss does not improve consecutively over twenty epochs. A full scan of hyperparameters for pre-training and downstream evaluation is not performed as this exceeds the scope of this paper and our available computational resources. However, we ensure that all models converge to a suitable solution by manually choosing an appropriate optimizer and tuning the learning rate and method-specific hyperparameters. The supplementary material contains an overview of the used hyperparameters for each SSL method.

Our implementation is based on PyTorch [25] and the official repositories of the introductory papers from the respective self-supervised methods. Our experiments are performed on an Nvidia DGX station, which features eight A100 GPUs, each with 40 GB of memory, 512 GB of system memory and a CPU with 64 cores. The code and models to reproduce our results are publicly available.

Training and evaluation protocols. All self-supervised methods are pre-trained on the pre-training dataset and evaluated during training on a validation set, for which a random subsample of the Fitzpatrick17k dataset [14] is used. After the models finished training, the pre-trained encoders were evaluated on unseen downstream tasks, following standard practice in SSL [13, 8, 5, 35].

To compare the representations learned by different pre-training strategies, we evaluate them using linear and k -nearest neighbor (kNN) evaluation on frozen features and fine-tuning the pre-trained encoder, similar to [5, 35]. The frozen evaluation was only carried out for the classification tasks since segmentation would require an up- or down-sampling, which would yield an unfair comparison since it is dependent on the dimension of the embedding. Fine-tuning was then performed on all downstream tasks. For fine-tuning, we initialize networks with the pre-trained weights, adapt them during training, and apply random resize cropping, horizontal and vertical flipping, random rotation and colour jitter to augment the data. A classification head is added to the pre-trained encoder for fine-tuning classification tasks. The head consists of dropout, batch normalization and a single linear layer to produce the class activations. The linear classification layer was added after the last average pooling layer for models using a ResNet backbone, and for ViT-based ones, we follow [5] and add the linear layer after the concatenation of the class token from the last four blocks in the model. For segmentation tasks, the pre-trained encoder is followed by a decoder to produce pixel-wise labels. The decoder is similar to a U-Net architecture [27] without the skip connections since ViT do not have different resolutions in their encoder and thus would not yield the same benefit as when using them with CNN. For linear and kNN evaluation on frozen embeddings, we do not apply any augmentation techniques and report performance on the central crop.

Tab. 1. Macro-averaged test F1 scores of pre-trained models reported for four dermatology diagnosis tasks. The arrows indicate if a method outperforms the baseline models, where \uparrow and \downarrow indicate out- or under-performance.

	PAD-UFES-20		HAM10000		Fitzpatrick17k		BodyLoc	
	lin.	kNN	lin.	kNN	lin.	kNN	lin.	kNN
ImageNet (RN-50)	52.5%	47.0%	54.5%	52.8%	51.1%	69.2%	62.7%	62.9%
ImageNet (ViT-T)	47.5%	43.7%	57.3%	52.0%	52.4%	65.9%	66.8%	65.0%
SimCLR (RN-50:IN)	34.4 %	31.2 %	34.5 %	31.0 %	40.3 %	43.6 %	55.2 %	47.3 %
ColorMe [20]	\downarrow 41.2%	\downarrow 32.2%	\downarrow 43.3%	\downarrow 37.0%	\uparrow 45.3%	\downarrow 56.5%	\downarrow 58.0%	\downarrow 51.7%
SimCLR [8]	\downarrow 31.2%	\downarrow 37.0%	\downarrow 27.1%	\downarrow 33.4%	\downarrow 43.0%	\downarrow 48.0%	\downarrow 39.4%	\downarrow 52.7%
BYOL [13]	\uparrow 49.8%	\uparrow 46.2%	\uparrow 48.0%	\uparrow 57.9%	\uparrow 54.1%	\downarrow 67.5%	\uparrow 70.0%	\uparrow 71.7%
DINO [5]	\uparrow 55.6%	\uparrow 50.8%	\uparrow 60.9%	\uparrow 60.6%	\uparrow 56.0%	\uparrow 69.6%	\uparrow 69.7%	\uparrow 68.1%
iBOT [35]	\uparrow 59.7%	\uparrow 48.0%	\uparrow 62.7%	\uparrow 61.1%	\uparrow 58.6%	\uparrow 70.3%	\uparrow 67.4%	\uparrow 67.1%

Tab. 2. Fine-tuned test performance of multiple pre-trained models reported for four classification- and two segmentation tasks. The results are obtained by varying the random seed and reporting the average performance and estimated uncertainty. Bold values indicate statistically significant superiority or equivalence against the other methods. The arrows indicate if a method outperforms the baseline models, where \uparrow and \downarrow indicate out- or under-performance.

	Test F1 Score				Test mIoU Score	
	PAD-UFES-20	HAM10000	Fitzpatrick17k	BodyLoc	ISIC 2018	PPP
ImageNet (RN-50)	61.5 \pm 1.5%	80.9 \pm 0.7%	75.3 \pm 0.5%	77.6 \pm 0.5%	79.7 \pm 0.3%	61.7 \pm 0.1%
ImageNet (ViT-T)	61.2 \pm 0.7%	78.3 \pm 0.8%	76.2 \pm 0.2%	79.4 \pm 0.6%	78.8 \pm 0.1%	63.0 \pm 0.2%
ColorMe [20]	\downarrow 58.4 \pm 1.2%	\downarrow 73.7 \pm 0.8%	\downarrow 69.3 \pm 0.7%	\downarrow 74.6 \pm 0.9%	\downarrow 78.5 \pm 0.2%	\uparrow 63.0 \pm 0.6%
SimCLR [8]	\downarrow 37.0 \pm 1.3%	\downarrow 40.9 \pm 1.7%	\downarrow 52.0 \pm 0.7%	\downarrow 73.5 \pm 0.4%	\downarrow 75.6 \pm 0.1%	\uparrow 62.8 \pm 0.2%
BYOL [13]	\downarrow 57.6 \pm 1.2%	\downarrow 69.2 \pm 0.8%	\downarrow 69.5 \pm 0.8%	\uparrow 76.7 \pm 1.0%	\downarrow 77.0 \pm 0.3%	\uparrow 66.2 \pm 0.1%
DINO [5]	\downarrow 57.7 \pm 1.3%	\downarrow 76.8 \pm 1.4%	\downarrow 73.8 \pm 0.3%	\downarrow 73.0 \pm 0.4%	\uparrow 80.2 \pm 0.1%	\downarrow 60.1 \pm 0.4%
iBOT [35]	\uparrow 65.6 \pm 0.9%	\uparrow 82.0 \pm 1.2%	\uparrow 78.9 \pm 0.5%	\uparrow 78.8 \pm 0.5%	\uparrow 81.1 \pm 0.2%	\downarrow 60.3 \pm 0.3%

Additionally, to better understand the utility of domain-specific pre-training in low-data regimes, we further train a simple kNN and linear classifier on a random subset of the classification task’s labelled data and evaluate them on the same hold-out test set as the evaluations above.

Baselines. To examine the influence of using domain-specific pre-training versus general-image pre-training, our primary baselines are supervised pre-trained models on ImageNet, specifically a supervised pre-trained RN-50 and ViT-T⁴. Further, to investigate the difference between domain-specific and domain-agnostic self-supervised pre-training, we use a SimCLR pre-trained RN-50 on ImageNet.

⁴ <https://huggingface.co/WinKawaks/vit-tiny-patch16-224>, accessed on 04.01.2023

4 Results

In table 1, we compare different pre-training methods on the classification downstream tasks in terms of frozen kNN and linear performance. Frozen evaluation investigates how well the pre-trained models separate an unseen dataset and thus answers the question of whether inherent properties of the downstream task have, to a certain extent, been learnt during pre-training. The results show that ColorMe and SimCLR underperform all three baseline methods across all tasks. The results further indicate that BYOL might yield a particular benefit, especially in larger data regimes such as BodyLoc. This suggests that models with a CNN backbone do not profit as much from domain-specific pre-training as the others in our setting and are better off using general features. On the other hand, the results from DINO and iBOT show that both methods outperform the baseline models, indicating that both models have profited from the domain-specific pre-training and learnt inherent properties useful for the downstream tasks at hand. A possible explanation for this behaviour is that CNN-based models have strong inductive biases incorporated in their architecture and thus benefit more from having general pre-trained weights than architectures with less bias, such as ViTs [22]. Another possible explanation for this significant case would be that both DINO and iBOT use a multi-crop augmentation strategy, which forces the model to focus on both global and local features. In the most significant case, iBOT improved the linear and kNN performance by 7% and 8%, respectively, compared to the best general-purpose pre-training.

Table 2 summarizes the fine-tuned performance on both classification and segmentation tasks. We repeated the fine-tuning of each method five times when varying the random seed to observe the fluctuation due to randomness in the splitting, augmentation and initialization and reported the mean and its uncertainty for each task. We further performed two-sided Student’s t -tests to check for statistical significance between different methods. The results show that ColorMe, SimCLR, and BYOL again underperform both baseline methods by a clear margin, indicating that domain-specific pre-training hurt the performance of the models. The significant performance difference between SimCLR and all other SSL methods might be caused by the self-similarity property of textural images, i.e. images of the same category have highly similar internal structures and textures. This property contradicts the contrastive loss, which requires an image to be similar to itself and dissimilar to others [28]. Unlike in the frozen evaluation, DINO performed worse than ImageNet pre-training. On the other hand, iBOT pre-training yielded the most benefit in terms of classification and segmentation performance. In the most significant case, for PAD-UFES-20, iBOT improved the fine-tuned performance by 4% compared to the best general-purpose pre-training. Further, we can observe a performance difference between the two supervised pre-training baselines. Specifically, RN-50 is performing better for smaller datasets such as PAD-UFES-20 and HAM10000, whereas ViT-T is performing better for bigger ones such as Fitzpatrick17k and BodyLoc, which is a similar behaviour as described in [11], i.e. ViTs excel when enough training data is available but are worse than ResNets in small data regimes.

Fig. 1. Results of a linear classifier on pre-trained representations when varying the number of training samples per class available for all classification tasks.

In figure 1, we compare pre-training methods by adding a linear classifier and varying the training dataset size for the classification tasks. The same experiment can be found in the supplementary materials for a kNN classifier. The figures show that domain-specific self-supervised pre-training can reduce the need for annotated samples on average by 50% and improve the test performance on average by 5% compared to the best baseline. In the most extreme case, for the HAM10000 dataset, ≈ 500 samples result in a higher score than using the entire dataset ($\approx 10^4/000$) with general-purpose pre-training.

5 Conclusion

This paper assesses the quality of domain-specific self-supervised pre-trained features compared to general-purpose ones across six selected medical imaging tasks, from which four are classification- and two are segmentation tasks. We evaluated five self-supervised learning methods, namely ColorMe, SimCLR, BYOL, DINO and iBOT in terms of their frozen kNN and linear as well as fine-tuned performance. The results show that ColorMe, SimCLR, BYOL did not outperform ImageNet features for the selected tasks. Among all self-supervised techniques, iBOT outperforms other methods on most datasets and evaluation protocols. The results indicate a significant benefit in using domain-specific self-supervised pre-training, especially in low-data regimes, to improve performance and reduce the need for annotated samples. In future work, we plan to explore how the amount of pre-training data influences the benefits of domain-specific self-supervised learning.

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A Supplementary Material

Tab. 3. Hyperparameters used for pre-training each SSL method, where “-” indicates that this parameter is not used.

Hyperparameter	ColorMe	SimCLR	BYOL	DINO	iBOT	iBOT (ISIC)
encoder_type	ResNet-50	ResNet-50	ResNet-50	ViT-Tiny	ViT-Tiny	ViT-Tiny
batch_size	200	640	60	260	224	224
epochs	100	100	100	100	100	100
optim	SGD	Adam	Adam	AdamW	AdamW	AdamW
lr	0.001	0.00003	0.003	0.0005	0.005	0.005
min_lr	-	1e-6	1e-6	1e-6	5e-4	5e-4
warmup_epochs_lr	-	10	10	10	10	10
weight_decay	-	1e-6	-	0.04	0.04	0.04
weight_decay_end	-	0.4	-	0.4	0.4	0.4
clip_grad	3.0	3.0	3.0	3.0	3.0	3.0
use_lr_scheduler	False	True	True	True	True	True
use_wd_scheduler	False	True	False	True	True	True
loss/weight_mse	10.0	-	-	-	-	-
loss/weight_kld	1.0	-	-	-	-	-
momentum_teacher	-	-	0.996	0.9995	0.996	0.996
global_crops_scale	-	-	-	(0.7, 1.)	(0.7, 1.)	(0.7, 1.)
local_crops_scale	-	-	-	(0.05, 0.4)	(0.05, 0.4)	(0.05, 0.4)
global_crops_number	-	-	-	2	2	2
local_crops_number	-	-	-	12	12	12

Fig. 2. Results of a kNN classifier on pre-trained representations when varying the number of training samples per class available for all classification tasks.

Tab. 4. Ablation study to investigate the influence of the pre-training dataset. We compared two iBOT models, one trained on the full dermatology dataset and one only trained on public ISIC challenges. The table shows macro-averaged test F1 scores for four dermatology diagnosis tasks.

	PAD-UFES-20		HAM10000		Fitzpatrick17k		BodyLoc	
	lin.	kNN	lin.	kNN	lin.	kNN	lin.	kNN
ImageNet (RN-50)	49.7%	47.0%	54.1%	52.8%	51.0%	69.2%	62.2%	62.9%
ImageNet (ViT-T)	47.9%	43.7%	50.6%	52.0%	53.7%	65.9%	62.4%	65.0%
SimCLR (RN-50:IN)	36.2 %	31.2 %	34.1 %	31.0 %	39.9 %	43.6 %	55.2 %	47.3 %
iBOT [35]	59.7%	48.0%	72.0%	61.1%	58.3%	70.3%	71.5%	67.1%
iBOT (ISIC) [35]	50.4%	44.1%	61.0%	61.5%	48.8%	64.5%	65.1%	62.0%

(a) PAD-UFES-20 (b) HAM10000 (c) Fitzpatrick17k (d) BodyLoc

(A) Linear classifier

(e) PAD-UFES-20 (f) HAM10000 (g) Fitzpatrick17k (h) BodyLoc

(B) k -nearest neighbor classifier

Fig. 3. Results of a linear (A) and kNN (B) classifier trained on pre-trained representations of iBOT and iBOT, trained on only ISIC data, when varying the number of training samples per class available for all classification tasks.

2.1 Peer Review

This paper investigates the influence of domain-specific self-supervised pre-training for digital dermatology by comparing five self-supervised methods against both supervised and self-supervised general-purpose pre-training across six medical tasks. They use a large collection of dermatology pictures consisting of clinical and dermoscopy images for pre-training. According to the authors, using domain-specific self-supervised features yields a performance increase and further reduces the need for annotated samples.

The pros of this paper are listed below:

- + An interesting study on the influence of domain-specific pre-training for digital dermatology
- + Evaluation of multiple recent self-supervised methods (ColorMe, BYOL, SimCLR, DINO, iBOT)
- + Comparison against multiple baselines, i.e. supervised and self-supervised general-purpose
- + Multiple downstream tasks used as evaluation, including segmentation

The cons of this paper are listed below:

- Reduction of annotated samples needs to be shown for fine-tuning
- There is only little information available on the choice of pre-training data and its influence
- Multiple other studies have mentioned an increase in robustness when using SSL
- Other studies have mentioned an improved convergence speed when using SSL

The primary concerns about this paper are directly related to the list of cons mentioned above. The statement about reducing the need for annotated samples is only based on the frozen linear performance and thus contains only limited information value since fine-tuning on a given task typically needs to be performed. The same experiment as for the linear evaluation should be repeated with fine-tuning, i.e. training on 5%, 10%, 50% and 100% of the data. Further, there is only limited information on the choice of the pre-training data. The authors mention that they use a combination of clinical and dermoscopy images because of their hypotheses that they contain similar patterns. However, do not investigate that statement any further. An ablation study on the influence of the pre-training data and their respective size would yield more insight and could verify or invalidate their assumption. Other studies have mentioned increased robustness when using self-supervised learning, which was never mentioned. The results also do not indicate any significant difference in robustness when repeating experiments with different random seeds. Additionally, other studies have noted an improved convergence speed, which was not investigated in this paper. A minor comment would be adding the standard deviations to the frozen linear and k -nearest-neighbour performance.

Chapter 3

Self-supervised pre-training as the next generation of providing automated dermatologic diagnosis

This chapter includes a letter to the editor about a potential paradigm shift from general-purpose supervised to domain-specific self-supervised transfer learning to be submitted to a medical journal in dermatology such as the Journal of Investigative Dermatology (JID)¹. According to the journals' guidelines, the submitted manuscript should contain a maximum of 1000 words, 15 references, two tables or figures and three printed pages. Similarly to the scientific article presented in chapter 2, the letter to the editor resulted from the continuation of prior work of the author's specialisation project (Gröger, 2022), which was accepted and presented at the IJCAI workshop on Scarce Data in Artificial Intelligence for Healthcare 2022 in Vienna (Gröger et al., 2022).

The primary motivation behind this letter to the editor was that ImageNet pre-training is widely used in digital dermatology to mitigate the lack of available data. This trend originated from the computer vision domain, where this principle of transfer learning from ImageNet has been widely studied and has been shown to increase performance and robustness. However, in recent years, there has been a paradigm shift from supervised to self-supervised pre-training. When applied to domain-specific data, this has shown remarkable performance, mainly caused by the fact that it does not inherit any bias present in the labels. Thus, this letter aims to raise awareness of this new pre-training strategy primarily targeted towards clinical dermatologists.

Remark. The author himself wrote the letter to the editor. However, multiple co-authors of the paper have contributed to the current report by reviewing, correcting and giving feedback on the points to improve. Additionally, some aspects have been peer-reviewed since the article continues a workshop contribution.

¹<https://www.jidonline.org/>, accessed on 26.01.2023

Self-supervised pre-training as the next generation of providing automated dermatologic diagnosis

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To the Editor

Visual object recognition with convolutional neural networks (CNNs) is the basis of most attempts to automate dermatologic diagnosis. These CNNs are often pre-trained on the 14-million-strong ImageNet database to compensate for the lack of dermatological image data and improve robustness [9]. This trend originated in the field of computer vision, where so-called “transfer learning” from ImageNet [5] was the *de facto* standard. In recent years, however, there has been a paradigm shift from supervised to self-supervised pre-training. Self-supervised learning (SSL) is a way of learning from data without explicit instructions or labels. Instead, it learns patterns from the data and uses them to perform a task, thus not inheriting any biases present in the labels. A simple example of a self-training task is predicting the rotation angle of an image, where the model is not given explicit information about the angle. Instead, it must use the structure of the image itself to determine the rotation. The availability of unlabelled datasets and the lack of labelled datasets have therefore been the main drivers for this new technique. Large-scale labelled datasets are rare in many domains and often very costly to produce. In the medical domain, for example, the high cost of obtaining expert annotations [3], the difficulty of getting multiple experts to agree on an answer [8], and annotation processes that must follow strict rules are the main limiting factors. In this letter, we report on our efforts to compare these two pre-training strategies. One technique is called “general purpose” and is based on ImageNet pre-training. The other is called “domain-specific self-supervised” and is pre-trained using DINO [2] on a large dermatology dataset consisting of 250’000 unlabelled dermoscopy and clinical images. DINO is a recent SSL technique that has shown remarkable performance in various medical imaging tasks [11]. For comparison, we used three unlabelled dermatology datasets: an ISIC melanoma dermoscopy ($\approx 10’000$ samples) [12], a small clinical

image ($\approx 2’000$ samples) [10], and a Fitzpatrick clinical image dataset ($\approx 17’000$ samples) [7]. We use a linear classifier to compare the performance of the pre-training strategies to test whether they have already learnt useful features for dermatology tasks. We also perform the same comparison on different fractions of the original training dataset to investigate the influence of the number of training samples. The results of this evaluation are shown in Figure 1. Across all three datasets, domain-specific self-supervised pre-training can reduce the need for annotated samples by an average of 50% and improve test performance by an average of 5%. In the most extreme case, for the ISIC melanoma dataset, ≈ 500 samples result in a higher score than using the entire dataset ($\approx 10’000$) with generic pre-training. Similarly, using the full dataset with domain-specific self-supervised pre-training can improve test performance by an additional 5%. Furthermore, we qualitatively investigate the differences between the pre-training strategies by visualising their focus on unseen images. The results shown in Figure 2 indicate that general-purpose pre-training focuses on global objects and domain-specific pre-training on textural components, which is beneficial in dermatology. In addition, the figures show that the general-purpose pre-training focuses on the corners of the images. Furthermore, when we examine the focus of the ImageNet example, we can see that general-purpose pre-training focuses on the object and neglects all other information. This property is known as the semantic collapse of supervised learning, meaning that it removes all information that is not necessary for classification [6]. In summary, we have shown that domain-specific SSL can improve performance and reduce the need for annotated samples, especially for smaller datasets. Furthermore, by visualising the focus of pre-training strategies, we have shown that the domain-specific self-supervised pre-training approach has learned more favourable properties for dermatology than the general-purpose counterpart. The investigated pre-training strategy is a fundamental principle and is, therefore, indepen-

*These authors contributed equally to this work

dent of specific applications, datasets, or network architectures. Additionally, we provide several domain-specific self-supervised models pre-trained on a large dermatology dataset, which should serve as a starting point for future dermatology tasks¹.

Data Availability Statement

The data that support the findings of this study are openly available at <https://github.com/mattgroh/fitzpatrick17k> [7], <https://data.mendeley.com/datasets/zr7vgbcyr2/1> [10], and <https://doi.org/10.7910/DVN/DBW86T> [12].

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Conflict of Interest Statement

A. A. Navarini declares being a consultant and advisor and/or receiving speaking fees and/or grants and/or served as an investigator in clinical trials for AbbVie, Almirall, Amgen, Biomed, BMS, Boehringer Ingelheim, Celgene, Eli Lilly, Galderma, GSK, LEO Pharma, Janssen-Cilag, MSD, Novartis, Pfizer, Pierre Fabre Pharma, Regeneron, Sandoz, Sanofi, and UCB.

Author Contributions Statement

Fabian Gröger: Conceptualization, Data Curation, Formal analysis, Investigation, Methodology, Project administration, Software, Validation, Visualization, Writing – Original Draft, Writing – Review & Editing. **Philippe Gottfrois:** Validation, Data Curation. **Ludovic Amruthalingam:** Validation. **Alvaro Gonzalez-Jimenez:** Validation. **Simone Lionetti:** Methodology, Validation, Writing - Review & Editing. **Alexander A. Navarini:** Resources, Supervision, Writing - Review & Editing. **Marc Pouly:** Methodology, Resources, Supervision, Writing - Review & Editing.

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Figure 1: Results of a linear classifier applied to the pre-trained representations when varying the number of training samples per class available. The results show that domain-specific pre-training significantly improves performance across varying sample sizes.

Figure 2: Visualisation of the focus from the pre-trained ImageNet (general-purpose) and DINO (domain-specific self-supervised) features for different examples of unseen datasets. The first column shows the input image, the second the focus, the third the focus as an overlay over the input image and the fourth the top-4 most representative patches. The figures show that general-purpose pre-training focuses on global objects, whereas domain-specific pre-training on texture components.

3.1 Peer Review

This letter discusses a possible paradigm shift from supervised domain-agnostic to self-supervised domain-specific pre-training. It compares the two paradigms, supervised ImageNet and self-supervised DINO pre-training, on three unseen dermatology datasets. They use a quantitative evaluation based on frozen linear evaluation and a qualitative evaluation based on focus visualisation to showcase the difference in both pre-training strategies. According to the authors, using self-supervised domain-specific pre-training significantly reduces the need for annotated samples and improves performance. Further, the self-attention visualisation shows a clear difference between the strategies.

The pros of this paper are listed below:

- + Multiple unseen downstream tasks as evaluation
- + Qualitative results do a great job showcasing the difference
- + Unseen samples for qualitative results from diverse datasets
- + Open-sourcing multiple pre-trained models

The cons of this paper are listed below:

- Reduction of annotated samples needs to be shown for fine-tuning
- No information about the fine-tuning performance
- It is not clear which models were compared and if they use the same architecture
- Some aspects of the paper might be difficult to understand for the clinical dermatologists

The primary concerns about this letter to the editor are directly related to the list of cons mentioned above. Similarly to the scientific article in chapter 2, the reduction statement only contains limited information for direct applicability since fine-tuning is needed to achieve high performance rather than only linear evaluation. Thus, there should be an ablation to verify if this statement is true when fine-tuning. Additionally, only information about these models' linear performance is available. However, since fine-tuning is still required, information about the performance difference would make it a stronger statement. Further, some details of the letter need clarification, for example, which architectures were compared and if these were the same for both strategies. Additionally, it is not clear how the "focus" is obtained. Finally, some technical aspects of the paper should be improved to make them better understandable to the general audience.

Chapter 4

MedClean: An Effort to Clean Up Dermatology Datasets

This chapter includes a scientific article about an automatic data quality assessment in medical imaging to be submitted to a computer science conference such as Machine Learning for Health (ML4H)¹ at NeurIPS (NIPS). The conference guidelines do not feature any page, reference or word limit. The project follows a recent initiative called Data-Centric AI², which aims to improve the quality of training data rather than doing extensive model and hyperparameter optimisation.

The primary motivation behind this scientific project was that multiple data quality issues in current medical benchmark datasets were found during the projects from chapter 2 and 3. These issues mainly consist of irrelevant samples (e.g. X-ray images in a clinical dermatology dataset) and many duplicate images. Furthermore, primary investigations showed that the same image could sometimes be found in the pre-defined training and test split. Thus, every model ever evaluated is positively biased. Therefore, this project aimed to develop a semi-automated cleaning pipeline to detect dataset quality issues.

Remark. The author himself wrote the scientific article. However, multiple co-authors of the paper have contributed to the current report by reviewing, correcting and giving feedback on the points to improve.

¹<https://ml4health.github.io/2022/>, accessed on 26.01.2023

²<https://landing.ai/data-centric-ai/>, accessed on 26.01.2023

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MedClean: An Effort to Clean Up Dermatology Datasets

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Abstract

It is a known fact that many popular benchmark datasets contain various problems, such as label errors, irrelevant samples or duplicates, leading to the fact that all models evaluated on them are optimistically biased. Although the medical domain is often known for its high-quality datasets resulting from standardised collection processes, the domain is not protected from these problems since they also involve large amounts of manual work, which is prone to errors. In this paper, we propose MedClean, a general semi-automatic procedure to clean up medical imaging datasets using recent advances from self-supervised learning and exploiting the learned latent space. By relying on self-supervised learning, our proposed method does not inherit any potential bias in the labels and instead focuses on the properties of the image data itself. We benchmark MedClean

against multiple baselines to showcase its competitive performance and apply it to popular dermatology datasets to provide more reliable benchmarks.

Keywords: Dataset cleaning; Self-supervised learning; Data-centric

1. Introduction

In traditional machine learning, data cleaning was an essential part of the development process, mainly because minor contaminations in the dataset, such as label errors, duplicates, irrelevant samples and missing values, significantly impacted the model's performance and robustness (Li et al., 2021). However, since the rise of deep learning, data cleaning has become less crucial as large models have shown to work well even if the dataset is noisy (Rolnick et al., 2018). Thus large parts of research focused on learning from noisy data (Natarajan et al., 2013)

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rather than fixing the data issues themselves. Moreover, validating and cleaning large-scale datasets is not straightforward, especially when considering high-dimensional data such as images, where manually checking the entire dataset is often infeasible because it exhausts available resources. Thus in many domains, much effort has been invested in curating large public image databases, often used as benchmarks to compare different approaches. However, the rapid growth of these image collections also comes with a sharp decrease in their quality and consistency since their collection often involves some degree of automation and thus is inherently prone to various errors (Sambasivan et al., 2021). For example, Northcutt et al. (2021) evaluated ten of the most used benchmark datasets and found an average of 3.4% label error rate, cautioning that this could destabilise machine learning benchmarks. If label errors occurred profusely, they could undermine the framework by which progress is measured.

In many domains, the need for large publicly available datasets is still one of the main limiting factors to the progress of artificial intelligence. In these low-data regimes, the influence and importance of having access to “clean” data is more critical since even fractional amounts of poor-quality data can substantially hamper performance (Karimi et al., 2020). For example, high-quality data is needed in the medical domain to train accurate and generalisable models and validate their performance, which clinics and patients can rely on. However, most practitioners focus on the quantity of data as a key performance driver and assume high-quality as given by the collection process. Thus even in this critical domain, many existing datasets are known to contain varying noise levels, which can substantially undermine the progress of learning algorithms (Daneshjou et al., 2023).

This paper proposes a new method to clean medical datasets by relying on recent advances in self-supervised learning (SSL) called “MedClean”. The proposed method lets practitioners gain insight into their curated datasets and helps improve model robustness and evaluation reliability. In this paper, we reformulate the problem of dataset cleaning to a ranking problem where experts can make a final decision based on the proposed suggestions from the method. Thus instead of focusing on learning from noisy data, we follow the recent data-centric initiative (Jarrahi et al., 2022) and aim to restore confidence in semi-automatically collected datasets. Additionally, by applying MedClean to well-known dermatology benchmark datasets, trust in the reported scores and conclusions should be improved. In summary, our contributions include the following:

- The proposal of a new dataset cleaning method called “MedClean” based on SSL, which can be used to find near-duplicates, irrelevant samples and label errors, and additionally yields a domain-specific pre-trained model that can be used for transfer learning.
- A performance analysis of the newly proposed cleaning method compared to competitive baselines.
- The application of MedClean to well-known dermatology benchmarks and open-sourced resources to clean and correct their errors.

To the best of our knowledge, there has not been a holistic framework to clean multiple dataset errors in a joint pipeline based on recent advances of self-supervised learning focused on low-data regimes such as the medical domain.

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2. Related Work

Data cleaning originates from the data management community and has been widely studied (Chu et al., 2016). More recently, dataset cleaning in combination with deep learning models emerged and has been an active area of research. This section discusses related work on finding irrelevant samples, near-duplicates, and label errors separately since no holistic framework exists to date.

One approach is to use deep learning to detect and remove outliers in a dataset. Outlier detection can be divided into unsupervised, supervised and semi-supervised-based detectors. Unsupervised detection methods assume that anomalies are located in low-density regions and can further be categorised into reconstruction-error-based (Hendrycks et al., 2019; Abati et al., 2019), classification-based (Ruff et al., 2018) and probabilistic detectors (Ren et al., 2019). Supervised detectors, which require full ground truth labels, can identify known anomalies but risk missing unknown anomalies (Chalapaty et al., 2019; Liang et al., 2020). Semi-supervised algorithms can capitalise the supervision from partial labels while keeping the ability to detect unseen types of anomalies. Prominent approaches include training on in-distribution data and detecting anomalies that deviate from the dataset representation learned during training (Akcay et al., 2019).

Another part of the research has focused on near-duplicate detection. Traditional approaches generate local representations by detecting points or regions of interest (Lowe, 2004) followed by matching (Ke et al., 2004). Most deep learning approaches follow a similar representation-matching strategy, where vectors from a deep network are extracted and utilized as global representations for content-based matching (Babenko et al., 2014). Another approach is to use a siamese

neural network to learn a similarity metric between pairs of records (Žbontar and LeCun, 2015).

Further research has focused on finding and fixing or excluding label errors. Most of these approaches are based on prediction-label agreement via confusion matrices by removing samples with a low recognition rate (Chen et al., 2019) or parts of the minority classes (Zhang et al., 2020). A recent approach based on deep learning utilizes supervised contrastive learning for label error correction (Huang et al., 2022). Another prominent method is to use confident learning for exact uncertainty quantification (Northcutt et al., 2022).

3. Methodology

Let $\mathcal{X} = \{(\mathbf{x}_i, l_i) \mid i \in \mathcal{I}\}$ be the dataset with index set $\mathcal{I} = \{1, \dots, N\}$, where $\mathbf{x}_i \in \mathbb{R}^{h \times w \times c}$ is the i -th sample with height h , width w and channels c , and $l_i \in \{1, \dots, C\}$ the i -th label. The feature extractor f with parameters θ maps a sample \mathbf{x}_i to the representation $\mathbf{e}_i = f(\mathbf{x}_i; \theta) \in \mathbb{R}^D$ where D denotes the latent dimension. The image of \mathcal{X} in the latent space is then $\mathcal{E} = \{\mathbf{e}_i \mid i \in \mathcal{I}\}$.

The weights θ of the feature extractor f are pre-trained on \mathcal{X} using self-supervised learning (SSL). The assumption is that SSL produces meaningful latent spaces by training features to be invariant to augmentations. Further, it does not suffer from the semantic collapse of supervised learning, which removes any information not necessary for class assignment (Fernandez et al., 2022).

In this work, we consider pre-trained features from SimCLR (Chen et al., 2020) and DINO (Caron et al., 2021), which have been shown to produce meaningful latent spaces (Fernandez et al., 2022; Wang and Isola, 2020). However, any SSL method can be used. As SimCLR has feature normalization built into the training objective, it is natural

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to compare points in the latent space using cosine similarity $\text{sim}(\mathbf{u}, \mathbf{v})$ and its associated distance scaled to $[0, 1]$, $\text{dist}(\mathbf{u}, \mathbf{v})$:

$$\text{sim}(\mathbf{u}, \mathbf{v}) = \frac{\mathbf{u}^\top \mathbf{v}}{\|\mathbf{u}\| \cdot \|\mathbf{v}\|}, \quad (1)$$

$$\text{dist}(\mathbf{u}, \mathbf{v}) = \frac{1 - \text{sim}(\mathbf{u}, \mathbf{v})}{2}. \quad (2)$$

To facilitate the comparison with DINO, we include L_2 normalization for the output features during training and inference.

Near-duplicate ranking. We define near duplicates as pairs of images which contain two views of identical objects. In this sense, exact duplicates are an easy special case of near duplicates. We rank potential near duplicates by sorting each pair of distinct samples $(i, j), i \neq j$ in ascending order according to the distance between their representations, $\text{dist}(\mathbf{e}_i, \mathbf{e}_j)$. Thus the first pair in the ranking has the smallest cosine distance to every other pair.

Label error ranking. Label errors are defined as samples assigned to the wrong class label. Similarly to near duplicates, we rank potential label errors by sorting samples in ascending order by their silhouette score (Rousseeuw, 1987) $\text{silh}(\mathbf{e}_i)$ with respect to label assignments. We recall that $\text{silh}(\mathbf{e}_i)$ is a measure of the similarity of a representation to its own cluster compared to any other cluster and is given by

$$\text{silh}(\mathbf{e}_i) = \frac{b(\mathbf{e}_i) - a(\mathbf{e}_i)}{\max(a(\mathbf{e}_i), b(\mathbf{e}_i))}, \quad (3)$$

where $a(\mathbf{e}_i)$ is the average distance between \mathbf{e}_i and all other points in the same cluster, and $b(\mathbf{e}_i)$ is the minimum average distance between \mathbf{e}_i and all points in any other cluster:

$$a(\mathbf{e}_i) = \frac{1}{c_i} \sum_{j \in \mathcal{I}} \text{dist}(\mathbf{e}_i, \mathbf{e}_j) \delta_{i,l_j}, \quad (4)$$

$$b(\mathbf{e}_i) = \min_{k \neq l_i} \frac{1}{c_k} \sum_{j \in \mathcal{I}} \text{dist}(\mathbf{e}_i, \mathbf{e}_j) \delta_{k,l_j}. \quad (5)$$

Here δ is the Kronecker delta and

$$c_k = \sum_{j \neq i} \delta_{kl_j}. \quad (6)$$

Irrelevant sample ranking. We define samples as irrelevant when they are not expected to produce reliable output in the context of the dataset. For example, this could be because the image is from a different modality or contains no object of interest. However, the definition of irrelevant samples highly depends on the considered dataset.

Unlike previous approaches, irrelevant sample ranking does not rely on a score with continuous values. Instead, it is induced by agglomerative clustering with single linkage (Gower and Ross, 1969). This is a hierarchical clustering method that starts with N clusters, one for each point \mathbf{e}_i in \mathcal{E} , and iteratively merges the clusters containing the two closest points as formalized in Algorithm 1. Samples are sorted by organising the resulting dendrogram such that in each merge, all elements of the cluster with fewer leaf nodes appear first, and allowing for ties.

4. Experimental Setup

Datasets. The datasets listed below are used for evaluating the proposed cleaning approach. They were chosen because of their high-quality nature since curation involved large amounts of manual correction and validation from domain experts. *Fitzpatrick17k (FP)* is a public benchmark dataset containing 16'577 clinical images with skin condition labels and skin type labels based on the Fitzpatrick scoring system (Groh et al., 2021). In this study, we used the middle granularity level of skin condition labels, which partitions the labels into nine disease categories. The images originate from two online dermatology atlases and thus are known to contain noise (Daneshjou et al., 2023). However, as a data quality check, they asked

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Algorithm 1: Agglomerative clustering using single linkage.

1. Initialize each representation e_i as a separate cluster $\mathcal{C}_i = \{e_i\}$ for $i = 1$ to N .
 2. Repeat until all data points are in a single cluster:
 - (a) Compute the distances $\text{dist}(\mathcal{C}_i, \mathcal{C}_j)$ between all pairs of clusters \mathcal{C}_i and \mathcal{C}_j using the linkage criterion: $\text{dist}(\mathcal{C}_i, \mathcal{C}_j) = \min(\text{dist}(e_k, e_l))$ where $e_k \in \mathcal{C}_i$ and $e_l \in \mathcal{C}_j$.
 - (b) Merge the two closest clusters \mathcal{C}_i and \mathcal{C}_j into a new cluster $\mathcal{C}_k = \mathcal{C}_i \cup \mathcal{C}_j$.
 - (c) Update the set of clusters to be the set of remaining clusters $\mathcal{C} = (\mathcal{C} - \{\mathcal{C}_i, \mathcal{C}_j\}) \cup \{\mathcal{C}_k\}$
-

two board-certified dermatologists to evaluate the dataset’s diagnostic accuracy of 3% (504 samples). This random subset of the dataset is referred to as the high-quality Fitzpatrick17k dataset and will be used for evaluation. *Diverse Dermatology Images (DDI)* is a public, deeply curated, and pathologically confirmed image dataset with diverse skin tones containing 656 clinical images from 570 unique patients for 78 common and uncommon diseases originating from pathology reports in the Stanford Clinics (Daneshjou et al., 2022).

Training Details. We use a randomly initialised vision transformer (ViT) tiny with a patch size of 16×16 as an encoder (Dosovitskiy et al., 2021) for both SimCLR and DINO pre-training. Additionally, we use the same ViT pre-trained using supervised learning on ImageNet to ablate the influence of self-supervised pre-training. For the respec-

tive latent representation, the output for the class token from the last layer of the encoder is used, which has the dimension of 192 for a ViT tiny. The self-supervised pre-training follows the same principle described in the introductory papers of the respective methods (Chen et al., 2020; Caron et al., 2021). However, since we are using self-supervised pre-training on small datasets compared to standard sizes of pre-training datasets, we adapted the augmentation strategy to increase the variability of samples seen during training. All models were pre-trained for 500 epochs on the respective dataset, and only minor hyperparameter tuning was performed to ensure that the model converged to a suitable solution. The Table 4 in the appendix contains a detailed overview of the hyperparameters for both pre-training strategies. The model input is resized to 224×224 pixels and normalized using the mean and standard deviation of ImageNet (Deng et al., 2009). Our implementation is based on PyTorch (Paszke et al., 2019) and the official repositories for both self-supervised methods. Our experiments are performed on an Nvidia DGX station, which features eight A100 GPUs, each with 40 GB of memory, 512 GB of system memory and a CPU with 64 cores. The code and models to reproduce our results are publicly available¹.

Evaluation Metrics. As we reformulate the problem from detection to ranking, the evaluation relies on ranking metrics rather than classification. Thus the proposed method and the baselines are evaluated in terms of AUROC, AP, Recall@ k and Precision@ k , following standard practice in evaluating ranking systems (Rendle, 2019).

Experiments. To compare the proposed cleaning method against existing baselines, we create synthetic datasets by altering real-

1. github.com/mse-thesis-dermatology/med-clean, accessed on 01.02.23

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Table 1: **Comparison of multiple cleaning methods.** Performance of various irrelevant detection models applied to different evaluation datasets. In the table, the first abbreviation indicates which benchmark dataset was used, i.e. DDI or high-quality Fitzpatrick17k (FP). The second refers to the contamination strategy, i.e. adding X-ray images (XR) or images from the combined medical images (CMED), applying medical augmentation (MED) or artefact augmentation (ARTE), changing the total label distribution (LBL) or altering the distribution of each class separately (LBLC).

Method		Contamination 10%								
Irrelevant Samples		DDI + XR		DDI + CMED		FP + XR		FP + CMED		
		AUROC	AP	AUROC	AP	AUROC	AP	AUROC	AP	
	IN + IsolationForest	89.5 %	37.0 %	89.6 %	52.3 %	88.1 %	37.2 %	96.3 %	74.8 %	
	IN + HBOS	92.5 %	46.7 %	80.7 %	42.9 %	84.3 %	27.3 %	94.0 %	69.7 %	
	IN + DeepSVDD	52.4 %	9.8 %	75.9 %	21.0 %	51.3 %	9.0 %	66.5 %	23.1 %	
	IN + ECOD	85.1 %	27.1 %	96.9 %	68.5 %	71.9 %	15.6 %	93.8 %	53.1 %	
	FastDup	7.3 %	4.9 %	43.8 %	26.6 %	4.5 %	4.9 %	95.3 %	80.7 %	
	MedClean (IN)	100.0 %	100.0 %	99.9 %	99.2 %	99.2 %	80.3 %	99.7 %	96.7 %	
	MedClean (SimCLR)	90.8 %	32.8 %	78.5 %	49.7 %	95.5 %	48.1 %	74.2 %	37.6 %	
	MedClean (DINO)	100.0 %	100.0 %	97.4 %	89.5 %	100.0 %	100.0 %	98.5 %	84.1 %	
Near-Duplicates		DDI + MED		DDI + ARTE		FP + MED		FP + ARTE		
		AUROC	AP	AUROC	AP	AUROC	AP	AUROC	AP	
	pHashing	69.2 %	9.8 %	68.9 %	33.4 %	71.6 %	12.5 %	80.5 %	30.6 %	
	SSIM	85.7 %	25.7 %	84.2 %	35.3 %	92.6 %	36.1 %	88.5 %	32.9 %	
	FastDup	58.6 %	10.0 %	59.6 %	5.6 %	56.1 %	7.2 %	52.9 %	8.9 %	
	MedClean (IN)	99.1 %	34.4 %	96.1 %	40.3 %	97.0 %	47.1 %	94.1 %	38.4 %	
	MedClean (SimCLR)	96.1 %	13.7 %	88.6 %	37.5 %	97.4 %	22.4 %	87.2 %	17.3 %	
	MedClean (DINO)	99.5 %	55.7 %	98.7 %	45.2 %	99.3 %	61.2 %	95.3 %	38.9 %	
	Label Errors		DDI + LBL		DDI + LBLC		FP + LBL		FP + LBLC	
			AUROC	AP	AUROC	AP	AUROC	AP	AUROC	AP
IN + Confident Learning		74.2 %	24.7 %	71.7 %	42.7 %	76.0 %	28.5 %	69.1 %	28.2 %	
FastDup		68.6 %	14.6 %	71.4 %	28.8 %	85.2 %	32.3 %	84.7 %	28.9 %	
MedClean (IN)		50.4 %	11.5 %	46.0 %	18.7 %	70.7 %	21.6 %	54.5 %	11.5 %	
MedClean (SimCLR)		39.6 %	8.0 %	42.8 %	16.0 %	56.3 %	17.7 %	47.2 %	13.2 %	
MedClean (DINO)		52.9 %	11.7 %	41.1 %	16.2 %	47.7 %	18.2 %	51.1 %	17.2 %	

world dermatology benchmarks and compare every contamination category separately. Specifically, we divide the evaluation into near duplicate, irrelevant sample and label error evaluation. All evaluation tasks are based on the abovementioned datasets: high-quality Fitzpatrick17k and DDI. The creation of the synthetic dataset is inspired by the noise present in the medical domain. For every evaluation category, we define two separate synthetic datasets, thus resulting in four evaluation datasets for every category and a total of twelve evaluations. These evaluations are then repeated for different percentages of contamination, i.e. 5% and 10%, inspired by real-world noise percentages (Han et al., 2022). Further, for every noise category, we consider different com-

petitive baselines which have shown to perform well on the given task. Since our proposed method is unsupervised, we compare only against unsupervised baselines. It is important to note that the proposed method first uses self-supervised pre-training on the dataset to clean. Thus for evaluation, the pre-training is performed on the contaminated dataset. Specifically, a separate model is trained for every noise category, contamination and synthetic dataset.

For the near-duplicate evaluation, we randomly choose a predefined percentage of samples from the original dataset and, for the first, augment them by using a pipeline consisting of random rotation, resizing, padding and Gaussian blur, referred to as *MED*, inspired by near-duplicates often found in med-

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ical contexts (see Figure 2(a)). For the second, we take a percentage of the dataset and alter them by adding different medical artefacts, consisting of different watermarks, colour bars and rulers, additionally followed by scaling the image and randomly adding additional images to create “mosaic” images, called *ARTE* (see Figure 2(b)). Detailed information about the configurations for both augmentation strategies can be found in Table 5. For constructing the irrelevant sample evaluation, we add a predefined percentage of different images to the original dataset. For the first synthetic dataset, we contaminated it by adding X-ray images of COVID-19 patients (Ozturk et al., 2020), referred to as *XR*. For the second, we sample from multiple datasets, consisting of surgical tools (Lavado, 2018), X-ray images (Ozturk et al., 2020), ImageNet samples (Deng et al., 2009), histopathological images (Spanhol et al., 2016), segmentation masks (Codella et al., 2019) and pictures of PowerPoint slides (Araujo et al., 2016), referred to as *CMED* (see Figure 1). For label error evaluation, we take a predefined percentage of samples of the original dataset and change their labels, referred to as *LBL*. When considering the initial class distribution and changing a predefined portion of each class, we refer to it as *LBLC*.

5. Results

Table 1 shows the results of different baseline methods compared to MedClean using supervised ImageNet features and self-supervised pre-training using SimCLR and DINO. The abovementioned synthetic evaluation datasets are used for evaluation with a contamination percentage of 10%. Table 3 in the appendix further includes results for 5% contamination. The results show that our proposed method outperforms the considered baseline methods for irrelevant-sample

Table 2: **Linear performance of pre-trained features.** Macro-averaged test F1 scores of pre-trained encoders reported for the DDI and Fitzpatrick17k (FP) dataset. The results are obtained by varying the random seed and reporting the average performance and standard error. All encoders use the same ViT tiny architecture. Here MedClean uses DINO pre-training.

Method	DDI	FP
Random	$52.5 \pm 1.0\%$	$28.9 \pm 0.2\%$
ImageNet	$63.6 \pm 1.1\%$	$52.3 \pm 0.1\%$
MedClean	$59.2 \pm 1.9\%$	$53.8 \pm 0.4\%$

and near-duplicate detection. However, the performance of label error detection is considerably lower, indicating that there is the possibility of improving the method. The results show that supervised ImageNet features perform surprisingly well for irrelevant sample detection. One possible explanation is that the underlying latent space only roughly needs to project the outliers further away from the bulk of the data for irrelevant detection to work. Since ImageNet has never seen images from the medical domain during training, it is likely projecting the bulk of the data into a similar region and the outliers further away. On the other hand, we can see that using SimCLR pre-training has not resulted in competitive results compared to the other two pre-training strategies. One possible explanation for this might be the size of the datasets used for pre-training, leading to the fact that SimCLR cannot see many different images needed to converge to a suitable solution. The proposed method is a holistic framework that can detect irrelevant samples, near-duplicates and label errors altogether. Thus to compare the pre-training strategies, the average performance across all contamination types and evaluation tasks is

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used, showing that, on average MedClean using DINO pre-training performs best.

Since MedClean relies on self-supervised learning to produce meaningful latent spaces, the learned features can further be used for transfer learning, similar to any other pre-trained model. Thus in Table 2, we compare these pre-trained features by evaluating them on their respective task. More specifically, we first apply MedClean with DINO pre-training on the entire DDI and Fitzpatrick17k (FP) dataset, which results in a ranking for the different contamination types and a pre-trained encoder for the respective dataset. These pre-trained features were then compared to a random and ImageNet initialised ViT tiny in terms of linear performance on the respective classification task of the datasets, i.e. a binary classification (benign/malignant) for DDI and multi-class classification for Fitzpatrick17k with three categories. The results show that ImageNet features perform better for the DDI task. In contrast, for the larger Fitzpatrick17k task, the features produced by MedClean are more beneficial, thus indicating a further benefit of using MedClean since the produced features used for cleaning can be recycled for the considered downstream task where they potentially improve the performance.

6. Identifying Errors in Benchmark Datasets

Manually checking entire datasets is infeasible in most cases, even for smaller datasets, since it requires multiple passes over the entire dataset and all combinations to find, for example, near-duplicates. Thus we applied MedClean to the DDI and Fitzpatrick17k datasets to check the prevalence of errors. Further, since MedClean produces a ranking for irrelevant samples, near-duplicates and label errors, we do not need to check the entire dataset manually but only the proposed

ranking until we stop finding errors. Figures 3 and 4 showcase the top seven images, i.e. the samples most likely being an error, of the respective contamination type. Further, by manually checking an extensive part of each ranking, we found approximately 1% of near-duplicates and 0.1% of irrelevant samples in the DDI dataset, which can be considered relatively clean. In the Fitzpatrick17k dataset, on the other hand, we found $\approx 15\%$ of near-duplicates and $\approx 0.15\%$ of irrelevant samples. Since there is no fixed train-test split of the Fitzpatrick17k dataset that considers these near-duplicates, random dataset splits suffer from a train-test leak. Thus all models evaluated on them are stark optimistically biased. Figure 5 shows multiple near-duplicates found in the dataset and also contains examples where MedClean produced incorrect results.

7. Conclusion

This paper proposes a novel semi-automatic data-cleaning strategy called MedClean based on self-supervised learning to detect irrelevant samples, near-duplicates and label errors. The proposed method was compared across multiple datasets and contamination categories against different baselines. The results show that MedClean is competitive with the considered baselines, especially for the irrelevant sample and near-duplicate detection. However, the performance of label error detection is significantly worse, indicating possibilities for improvement. Further, the cleaning strategy was applied to popular dermatology benchmark datasets, where multiple dataset issues were found, such as irrelevant samples and near-duplicates. For example, in the case of the Fitzpatrick17k dataset, an astonishing 15% of duplicates were found.

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Figure 1: **Visualisation of irrelevant samples.** Random sample of irrelevant samples from the *CMED* contamination strategy, which will be added to a respective dataset. The images originate from multiple datasets, consisting of surgical tools (Lavado, 2018), X-ray images (Ozturk et al., 2020), ImageNet samples (Deng et al., 2009), histopathological images (Spanhol et al., 2016), segmentation masks (Codella et al., 2019) and pictures of PowerPoint slides (Araujo et al., 2016).

Table 3: **Comparison of multiple cleaning methods.** Performance of various irrelevant detection models applied to varying contamination rates of different datasets. In the table, the first abbreviation indicates which benchmark dataset was used, i.e. DDI or high-quality Fitzpatrick17k (FP). The second refers to the contamination strategy, i.e. adding X-ray images (XR) or images from the combined medical images (CMED), applying medical augmentation (MED) or artefact augmentation (ARTE), changing the total label distribution (LBL) or altering the distribution of each class separately (LBLC).

Method	Contamination 5%												Contamination 10%											
	DDI + XR		DDI + CMED		FP + XR		FP + CMED		DDI + XR		DDI + CMED		FP + XR		FP + CMED									
	AUROC	AP	AUROC	AP	AUROC	AP	AUROC	AP	AUROC	AP	AUROC	AP	AUROC	AP	AUROC	AP								
Irrelevant Samples	IN + IsotaintForest	92.3 %	26.9 %	91.8 %	53.1 %	81.5 %	12.8 %	96.3 %	68.4 %	89.5 %	37.0 %	89.6 %	52.3 %	88.1 %	37.2 %	96.3 %	74.8 %							
	IN + HBOS	95.4 %	47.4 %	78.9 %	35.3 %	86.5 %	16.9 %	94.3 %	60.1 %	92.5 %	46.7 %	80.7 %	42.9 %	84.3 %	27.3 %	94.0 %	69.7 %							
	IN + DeepSVDD	71.3 %	10.5 %	69.4 %	11.9 %	85.8 %	19.2 %	60.6 %	11.4 %	52.4 %	9.8 %	75.9 %	21.0 %	51.3 %	9.0 %	66.5 %	23.1 %							
	IN + ECOD	91.5 %	28.4 %	97.9 %	68.2 %	79.7 %	12.1 %	94.3 %	42.9 %	85.1 %	27.1 %	96.9 %	68.5 %	71.9 %	15.6 %	95.3 %	53.1 %							
	FeatDup	9.7 %	2.7 %	74.6 %	45.2 %	7.5 %	2.7 %	99.2 %	86.8 %	7.3 %	4.9 %	43.8 %	26.6 %	4.5 %	4.9 %	95.3 %	80.7 %							
Near-Duplicates	MedClean (IN)	100.0 %	100.0 %	100.0 %	100.0 %	99.2 %	70.6 %	99.9 %	98.8 %	100.0 %	100.0 %	99.9 %	99.2 %	99.2 %	80.3 %	99.7 %	96.7 %	96.7 %						
	MedClean (ShinCLR)	91.8 %	49.0 %	82.6 %	32.7 %	96.0 %	38.4 %	93.8 %	42.4 %	90.8 %	32.8 %	78.5 %	49.7 %	95.5 %	48.1 %	74.2 %	37.6 %							
	MedClean (DINO)	100.0 %	100.0 %	98.9 %	92.8 %	100.0 %	100.0 %	99.1 %	83.2 %	100.0 %	100.0 %	97.4 %	89.5 %	100.0 %	100.0 %	98.5 %	84.1 %							
Label Errors	IN + Confident Learning	73.2 %	16.4 %	67.7 %	39.1 %	75.5 %	17.3 %	76.5 %	23.9 %	74.2 %	24.7 %	71.7 %	42.7 %	76.0 %	32.3 %	69.1 %	28.3 %							
	FeatDup	77.9 %	12.9 %	73.8 %	26.3 %	82.8 %	17.3 %	86.2 %	22.6 %	68.6 %	14.6 %	71.4 %	28.8 %	85.2 %	32.3 %	84.7 %	28.9 %							
	MedClean (IN)	58.1 %	10.0 %	46.2 %	17.0 %	44.3 %	4.9 %	62.6 %	16.0 %	50.4 %	11.5 %	46.0 %	18.7 %	70.7 %	21.6 %	54.5 %	11.5 %							
	MedClean (ShinCLR)	50.9 %	6.9 %	42.8 %	14.0 %	54.2 %	5.8 %	46.7 %	10.5 %	39.6 %	8.0 %	42.8 %	16.0 %	56.3 %	17.7 %	47.7 %	13.2 %							
	MedClean (DINO)	57.8 %	11.0 %	48.3 %	15.4 %	50.5 %	10.4 %	62.5 %	7.6 %	52.9 %	11.7 %	41.1 %	16.2 %	47.7 %	18.2 %	51.1 %	17.2 %							

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Table 4: **Pre-training hyperparameters.** Hyperparameters used for pre-training using SimCLR and DINO on the dataset to clean. Here “-” indicates that the respective parameter is not used for the pre-training strategy. Parameters not given in this list follow the introductory paper. More detailed information about the hyperparameters can be found in the open-sourced codebase.

Hyperparameter	SimCLR	DINO
Batch size	90	64
Epochs	500	500
Optimizer	Adam	AdamW
Learning rate	0.001	0.0005
Min. learning rate	1e-6	1e-6
Weight decay	0.04	0.04
Weight decay end	0.4	0.4
Warmup epochs	10	10
Momentum teacher	-	0.996
Clip grad.	3.0	3.0
Base model	ViT tiny	ViT tiny
Model embedding dim.	192	192
Model output dim.	128	4096
Model patch size	16	16
Model drop path rate	0.1	0.1
Norm last layer	-	True
Global crops scale	-	(0.7, 1.)
Local crops scale	-	(0.05, 0.4)
Global crops number	-	2
Local crops number	-	12
Warmup teacher temp.	-	0.04
Teacher temp.	-	0.04
Warmup teacher temp. epochs	-	30
Contrastive temp.	0.5	-

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(a) MedAugment (MED)

(b) ArtefactAugment (ARTE)

Figure 2: **Visualisation of the near-duplicate augmentation strategies.** Random samples of near-duplicates added to the respective dataset for both augmentation strategies used to evaluate near-duplicate detection. Figure 2(a) shows examples of the MedAugment strategy (MED), which consists of random rotation, resizing, applying padding and Gaussian blur. Figure 2(b) shows examples of the ArtefactAugment strategy (ARTE), which consists of adding different medical artefacts featuring different watermarks, colour bars and rulers and then scaling the image and randomly adding additional images to create “mosaic” images. Images one, two and three show examples of these “mosaic” images.

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Near-Duplicate Ranking

Irrelevant Samples Ranking

Label Error Ranking

Figure 3: **Visualisation of MedClean applied to DDI.** The figure shows the near-duplicate, irrelevant samples and label error ranking for the DDI dataset (Daneshjou et al., 2022). The results show that multiple near-duplicates, irrelevant samples and label errors are present in the dataset.

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Near-Duplicate Ranking

Irrelevant Samples Ranking

Label Error Ranking

Figure 4: **Visualisation of MedClean applied to Fitzpatrick17k.** The figure shows the near-duplicate, irrelevant samples and label error ranking for the Fitzpatrick17k dataset (Groh et al., 2021). The results show that multiple near-duplicates, irrelevant samples and label errors are present in the dataset.

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Figure 5: **Visualisation of multiple Fitzpatrick17k near-duplicates.** The figure shows multiple near-duplicates found in the Fitzpatrick17k dataset (Groh et al., 2021). Figures 5(a) and 5(b) show that MedClean can find near-duplicates where the images were anonymised. Further, figures 5(c) and 5(d) show extreme cases of near-duplicates where the method found crops of the same image. Finally, figures 5(e) and 5(f) show examples where the near-duplicate detection failed.

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Table 5: **Near-duplicate augmentation strategy hyperparameters.** Hyperparameters used for the MedAugment (MED) and ArtefactAugment (ARTE) strategies. Here “-” indicates that the respective parameter is not used for the augmentation. More detailed information about the hyperparameters can be found in the open-sourced codebase.

Hyperparameter	MedAugment (MED)	ArtefactAugment (ARTE)
Rotation proba.	0.5	-
Padding proba.	0.5	-
Blur proba.	0.5	-
Rotation degree range	(0, 180)	-
Scale range	(0.5, 0.9)	-
Padding	3	-
Gaussian kernel size	5	-
Watermark proba.	-	0.5
Colorbar proba.	-	0.5
Mosaic proba.	-	0.5
Watermark max. scale	-	0.5
Mosaic max. scale	-	0.5

4.1 Peer Review

This paper proposes a novel semi-automatic data-cleaning strategy based on self-supervised learning to detect irrelevant samples, duplicates and label errors, called MedClean. To evaluate the proposed method, it is compared against multiple baselines in each of the three dataset contamination categories separately. For comparison, they use synthetic datasets featuring diverse issues inspired by the contamination found in the medical domain. The results show that the proposed method is competitive with the considered baselines.

The pros of this paper are listed below:

- + Novel data cleaning strategy for cleaning multiple dataset issues
- + Appliance of MedClean to well-known dermatology benchmarks
- + Reformulation of cleaning as a ranking problem
- + Comparison against multiple competitive baselines for each contamination type

The cons of this paper are listed below:

- Ablation study on the architecture, normalisation strategy, similarity measure and embedding dimension
- Scaling of the proposed method when varying the contamination
- Evaluation only uses synthetic noise
- Label error detection results are not competitive

The primary concerns about this paper are directly related to the list of cons mentioned above. There is little ablation about multiple aspects of the proposed method. For example, no information is given on the influence of the architecture, normalisation strategy or embedding dimension. Further, since the results directly using ImageNet features showed competitive results, an ablation on the effect of using pre-trained features for initialising the models would be beneficial. Further, more information is needed on how the method performs in extreme cases, for example, when only adding minor or plenary contamination. Additionally, an investigation of the influence of the combined medical irrelevant samples would give more insights into answering questions such as which are the most challenging samples to detect. The paper evaluates different methods across multiple datasets. However, all of these include adding synthetic noise. Thus, an evaluation of real-world errors would significantly improve the contribution. Finally, the results given by the comparison show that the method is competitive with others but is performing significantly weaker for label errors. Thus, there is still room for improvement. Further, the manual check of the ranking for the different benchmark datasets needs to be performed by domain experts to produce a meaningful outcome. Additionally, label errors are never mentioned, most likely because the performance of MedClean in this category needs to be improved. However, for a stronger publication, they should also be evaluated. A minor comment would be to visualise the sparse correspondence for duplicate detection to showcase the method’s validity, similar to what was done in Zhou et al. (2022). Another minor comment is to add standard deviations to the evaluation, enabling an overview of the robustness of the methods.

Chapter 5

Discussion

This chapter provides an outlook regarding future work in section 5.1 and discusses the results of the different subprojects in section 5.2.

5.1 Outlook

Several aspects could potentially improve each scientific article, as discussed in the respective review of each chapter (see Section 2.1, 3.1 and 4.1). Additionally, further studies could be carried out based on the results of the subprojects. Since the improvements have already been discussed in each chapter, the outlook below focuses on further studies and experiments rather than specific improvements. The section is divided into the two subprojects carried out in this thesis.

Subproject 1: Self-supervised pre-training for dermatological imaging

Investigation of learned embedding space. During the project, we found that domain-specific self-supervised pre-training has learned more favourable properties for dermatology than supervised and self-supervised general pre-training. However, a thorough investigation of the learned embedding space has yet to be performed. By applying clustering algorithms, one could investigate how many clusters were built in the latent space representation of a dataset and assess if they correspond to the dataset labels. Further investigation of the similarity of samples in each cluster would yield insights into the learning process. Additionally, one could evaluate if specific dataset categories were split into multiple distinct clusters and, in cooperation with a dermatologist, come up with possible explanations.

Investigation of domain adaption. One of the biggest problems in dermatology is domain adaption since the training data distribution and the final application data distribution are likely to differ and will often change over time. Thus, models that can adapt to unseen domains are often required. We hypothesise that using models pre-trained on dermatology data can lead to better generalisation to unseen domains than those pre-trained on natural image datasets since they do not suffer from semantic collapse (Doersch et al., 2021). In future experiments, we thus want to examine if this hypothesis can be verified and how different the domains can be to produce reasonable results still.

Subproject 2: Data-centric approach to medical imaging

Confidence score. During the project, we found that different layers of the encoder produce similar but unequal embedding spaces. Thus, we want to investigate how we can exploit this property to produce a confidence score for the ranking, which would yield additional benefits for the semi-automatic application of MedClean. Similar approaches have been used in outlier detection to produce a confidence score (Lee et al., 2018).

Inference behaviour. The proposed method for cleaning can also be used at inference, where it can be run as a quality check before the actual model inference. For example, for each image given, MedClean could produce a score indicating how likely the given sample is a duplicate or irrelevant

sample compared to the considered dataset. This would increase the confidence of models applied in clinical settings since they could then only produce results for images similar enough to the initial dataset.

5.2 Conclusion

This thesis aimed to contribute to the research landscape of deep learning in combination with digital dermatology by producing three scientific articles in the domains of self-supervised learning and dataset cleaning for medical imaging. The first subproject resulted in two scientific papers, one targeted towards computer scientists (see Chapter 2) and one targeted towards medical doctors and clinicians (see Chapter 3). The first article assessed the quality of domain-specific self-supervised pre-trained features compared to general-purpose ones by comparing them across six selected medical imaging tasks and found that domain-specific self-supervised pre-training yielded a significant benefit, especially in low-data regimes, in terms of improving performance and reducing the need for annotated samples. Similarly, the second article compared domain-specific self-supervised with general-purpose features by focusing on qualitative evaluations. Visualising the focus of different pre-training strategies has shown that the domain-specific self-supervised pre-training approach has learned more favourable properties for dermatology than the general-purpose counterpart since it focused on local features such as textural components. The second subproject resulted in one scientific article targeted towards computer scientists (see Chapter 4), which introduced a novel semi-automatic data cleaning strategy based on self-supervised learning that can detect irrelevant samples, duplicates and label errors in a medical dataset and is producing reasonable results even in low-data regimes. The results indicate that the proposed strategy performs well on many tasks compared to competitive baselines from each dataset contamination category.

Appendix A

Appendix

A.1 Task definition

This section contains the original task definition that was submitted to the MSE-Secretariat at the start of the thesis.

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